

Analysing survey nonresponse: how objectivity and geography affect response rate

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GISRUK 2025

Summary

Survey nonresponse rates are a growing issue, affecting the reliability of statistics. Nonresponses are typically handled by imputation or deletion, assuming randomness. However, respondents may avoid certain questions based on their subjectivity or measurability. This study explores nonresponse patterns in relation to the objectivity or subjectivity of variables. It finds that for highly subjective questions, like health status, respondents are more likely to choose "don't know," while for objective questions, like age, they opt for "prefer not to say." These findings could help improve nonresponse assessment and boost response rates.

KEYWORDS: Survey nonresponses; subjective and objective measurement; survey design.

1 Introduction

Survey nonresponse is a growing problem. (Wang et al., 2015) and (Yan and Curtin, 2010) have shown a growing tendency for people not to respond - "unit nonresponse", or to only partially respond - "item nonresponse". Explanations include respondents' lack of time, interest, willingness or trust towards the survey, an inability to reach the respondent, or survey non-coverage, questionnaire skipping, interruption, and a refusal to provide specific information (Montagni et al., 2019). Nonresponses can cause biased results, inaccurate data, reduced validity of findings, and in general impair the applicability of statistics. Hence, the Office for National Statistics (ONS) has just committed to spending £8 million to improve response rates in the Labour Force Survey (Richard Partington, 2025).

Respondents opting not to answer a question can choose between a blank response, "I don't know", "I'm not sure", and "I don't want to answer" (not all options are always available) (Montagni et al., 2019). Attempts to force a response by making the question mandatory risks abandonment of the survey, or the selection of a spurious answer in order to continue, particularly if it is remunerated (Kroh, 2006).

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Some questions, such as age, are almost always matters of objective fact, evidence, immutable, and have clear answers. Others, such as marital status are matters of choice and may be less clear (Fields, 2014). This can be further modified by how quantifiable the answer is, with more quantifiable being associated in this case with greater objectivity. Whatever their view or later opinion, a respondent’s age is immutable and quantitative. In contrast, marital status can be changed and may be subjective. Accordingly, it is possible to rank these questions on a scale from most objective and quantitative, to most subjective and qualitative.

It is plausible that the respondents choose different approaches to avoid answering different types of questions depending on how objective and measurable the variables are. Therefore, this study looks at alternative ways of nonresponse assessment with respect to the objectivity and subjectivity levels of the variable. This may help diagnose approaches that will help boost response rates.

The data used in this study is the Financial Lives Survey, 2020, of the United Kingdom Financial Conduct Authority and was sourced from the Consumer Data Research Centre an Economic and Social Research Council Data Investment. It comprises a selection of responses to a 2020 survey on consumers’ attitudes, experiences and holdings of financial products. The survey uses Lower Super Output Area (LSOA) as primary sampling units and contains very high quality data from 13,965 individuals from England and Wales.

2 Analysis

2.1 Selected variable descriptions

The variables used in this analysis have been chosen to represent different levels of objectivity, as described in section 1. Accordingly, only demographic questions have been considered to eliminate “I’m not sure” nonresponses. Additionally, any questions with “Blank” responses have been omitted to focus on the “Prefer not to say” (PNTS) or “Don’t know” (DK) binary selection. Finally, to remove survey design as a possible confounder, only the questions with both PNTS and DK responses have been considered.

To represent the objective option the variable “*How many adults aged 18 or over, including yourself, are currently living in your household?*” (abbreviated to “Number of adults in household”) was chosen, with “*Do you have any physical or mental health condition(s) or illness(es) which have lasted or you expect to last for 12 months or more?*” (abbreviated to “Health status”) for the subjective option. Both represent questions for which the correct, definite answer is knowable. The “Number of adults in household” responses are integers, ranging from 1 to 10, whereas there are 4 categories of responses for “Health status” – Don’t know; No; Prefer not to say; and Yes.

The analysis will focus on the nature of the nonresponses for each question, ignoring the valid responses.

2.2 Results

The number of PNTS and DK nonresponses for each of the two questions are shown in Figure 1. This shows that there is a very different balance between the PNTS and DK responses for the

two questions. Although the PNTS were of similar magnitude there were far more DK for Health Status.

Table 1: Nonresponse components of the selected two questions.

Question	Prefer not to say	Don't know	Ratio of PNTS to DK
Number of adults in household	718	32	22.4
Health status	858	293	2.9

As can be expected there is a level of aspatial correlation between the two variables, as assessed using Pearson Correlation. At 0.1926, this was found to be relatively low.

To further analyse the nonresponses the data was coded as follows: PNTS was coded 1, DK was coded 2 and all other responses were coded 0. There was no other type of nonresponse for these variables. The plot of nonresponses for the “Number of adults in household” question is given in Figure 1 whereas the plot of nonresponses to the question “Health status” is given in Figure 2. Mapping the missing data in this way allows a representation of “absence”, as described by Robinson (2019). Interestingly, there appears to be clusters of nonresponses associated with specific areas, for instance North-West Wales around Anglesey, as shown in Figure 3. Note that owing to their higher population densities some urban LSOA are too small to see on these maps.

Having found an apparent difference in the ratios of PNTS to DK nonresponses between the two variables it is necessary to check if this difference is statistically significant. Two tests are used to assess this: Pearson’s Chi-squared test and Barnard’s test, with a Null hypothesis of no difference. The results of these tests are given in table 2. In both cases the Null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the Alternative hypothesis that there is a difference between these two sets of nonresponses.

Table 2: Tests for statistical difference between the PNTS and DK counts for the questions “Number of adults in the household” and “Health status”.

Test	Test statistic	p-value
χ^2	142.36	$< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Barnard	-11.99	1.08×10^{-23}

A test was then carried out for a relationship between the nonresponses and economic conditions. A useful indicator of economic conditions is the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD), which ranks the deprivation of LSOA areas from the most to the least deprived. In this dataset the most deprived area is ranked 4 whereas the least deprived area is ranked 32,840 from among all England and Wales LSOA. A Pearson correlation test was used to carry out this comparison; the results are given in Table 3.

These data show little evidence of a correlation between either of the six different data series and the IMD, as all correlations have an absolute value of less than 0.1.

Figure 1: Plot of the different nonresponses for “Number of adults in household” question, where RED (0) represents a valid response; BLUE (1) represents “Prefer not to say”; and GREEN (2) represents “Don’t know”.

Table 3: Correlation between the variable nonresponses and the Index of Multiple Deprivation (Rank)

Correlation	Both NR	PNTS only	DK only
Number of adults in the household to IMD (all NR)	-0.0653	-0.0521	-0.0464
Health status to IMD (all NR)	-0.0817	-0.0556	-0.0584

Figure 2: Plot of the different nonresponses for “Health status” question, where RED (0) represents a valid response; BLUE (1) represents “Prefer not to say”; and GREEN (2) represents “Don’t know”.

Figure 3: Plot by LSOA of the different nonresponses to both questions for the Anglesey area. In these maps 0 represents a valid response, 1 represents “Prefer not to say” and 2, “Don’t know”. Non-integer values indicate more than one response type is present in a given LSOA.

3 Discussion

From Table 1 it can be seen that more “Don’t know” answers are associated with the subjective than objective question. This may be owing to “Don’t know” not being considered a reasonable response for objective questions. When tested this difference was found to be statistically significant, although the small count for the objective question may have an impact on the statistical analysis of the data.

Given the lack of evidence for an influence from economic conditions it is an open question what is driving this difference. Mapping the nonresponses hints at possible geographic clustering, although it is difficult to see what would be driving this. It is possible that the structural nature of the question and the survey design could be a part of the answer. Questions on more subjective topics may also carry an additional social or psychological burden that impacts on giving a correct answer, even if a “Prefer not to say” option is available.

This study therefore suggests that survey nonresponses can be evaluated in terms of dimensions other than randomness, or the willingness or ability to answer. This study concerned two types of questions which may have different level of objectivity. The count for “Don’t Know” seems to be higher for questions measuring a variable with a higher level of subjectivity, e.g. “Health status”. This may also reflect concerns about, rather than actual knowledge of, health issues. This “concern” aspect may also be a useful metric for future studies.

This is only one set of analyses on two variables from a single high-quality, dataset. Further work is required to explore this aspect of survey nonresponse in greater depth.

4 Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support from the UK Research and Innovation Future Leaders Fellowships "Missing Data as Useful Data", grant number MR/Y011856/1. The data for this research have been provided by the Consumer Data Research Centre, an ESRC Data Investment, under project ID CDRC 1434, ES/L011840/1; ES/L011891/1.

5 Biography

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